

PARENTS' SUPPORT AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE ON PRINTED MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING IN SCIENCE SUBJECT IN AN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION CONTEXT

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Parents' Support and Academic Performance on Printed Modular Distance Learning in Science Subject in an Elementary Education Context

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Abstract

This study sought to answer how often do the parents support their Grade 5 pupils as to Monitoring, Volunteering, Involvement, Progress, and Extra Help and looked for its significant influence on the level of academic performance of the pupils in their Science subject using vernacular-translated questionnaire. After identifying the types of the parents supports, the level of occurrence was then asked to the parent-respondents through the questionnaire. Then, the retrieval of the pupils' grades was done with the full consent of the parents. The frequency count, weighted mean, and Chi-square test were the statistical tools used to answer the problems posed in the study. Findings divulged that among the identified parents' supports as to monitoring, volunteering, involvement, progress, and extra help, the last one which is the extra help (look for the materials needed for the completion of the child's activities and modules: WIFI, and others) gained a frequency count of 91 which ranks as first. While, on the level of occurrences of the identified parents' supports, only Progress type of parents' support is interpreted as sometimes being done by the parents to their child with a mean of 3.12; while the rest of the types of parents' supports are often done by the parents (monitoring – 4.02; Volunteering – 4.16; Involvement – 4.01; and Extra Help – 4.03). On the other hand, the level of the academic performance of Grade 5 pupils in Science subject got the average of 4.19 which means a very satisfactory grade. Lastly, on the test of significant influence on the level of occurrence of the parents' support and the academic performance of the Grade 5 pupils in Science subject, the result reveals that all types of parents' support only monitoring and extra help types contribute significant relationship on the level of occurrence of the parents' support and the students' academic performance in their science subject with a p-value lesser than 0.005 level of significance of 0.001 and 0.003; while volunteering, progress, and involvement do not contribute any significant findings since the p-value are greater than 0.005 level of significance, that are 0.171, 0.740, and 0.680 respectively. This study suggests that a parent shall continuously support their child in terms of monitoring and extra help types of parents' support since it means a lot on their very satisfactory grades.

Keywords: *parents' support, academic performance, printed distance modular learning, elementary education*

Introduction

The world recently struggled against the Corona virus Disease (COVID-19) that is caused by the 2019-novel Corona virus (2019-nCoV) that has underestimated its dangers (Zahar, 2020). This has resulted in restrictions on the movement of people. A Work-From-Home (WFH) scheme is applied to private and government workers with the exception to the skeletal workforce that consists of uniformed personnel such as Philippine National Police, Armed Forces of the Philippines, and Philippine Coast Guard (Medialdea, 2020).

In education sectors, in a virtual press briefing dated on August 14, 2020, Department of Education Secretary Leonor Briones announced that the opening of the school year had been moved from August 24 to October 5, 2020. Pres. Rodrigo Duterte has implemented the decision pursuant to the recommendation of the Department of Education (DepEd) (Tinga, 2020).

In lieu to this, modular learning modality has been implemented, a sudden shift from face-to-face classroom instruction. Modular learning modality has been crafted by the DepEd to address suffice the academic needs of the pupils in terms of this pandemic, however, this modality expects greater participation from the parents or guardians of individual pupils, since they are the nearest MKO (More Knowledgeable Others) as Lev Vygotsky theorized to assist their child in their sudden change of learning and especially to science subject.

Thus, these reasons drive the researchers to study the parents' support and participation on science modular learning modality of Grade 5 pupils and its influence to their science subject academic performance.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions posed in the study:

1. What are the levels of parents' supports to their Grade 5 pupils?
2. How often do their parents participate in supporting their child in their modular distance learning modality?
3. What is the level of the academic performance of Grade 5 pupils?
4. Is there a significant influence on the level of occurrence of the parents' support and their Grade 5 pupils' academic performance?

Literature Review

On parents' role

In a distance learning approach, parents would have to play an active role in the learning process. They would be the one to facilitate and guide their children through the modular lessons that would be sent to pupils while doing remote learning. Moreover, as (Comer & Haynes, 2017) states that children learn best when the significant adults in their lives -- parents, teachers, and other family and community members -- work together to encourage and support them. This basic fact should be a guiding principle as we think about how schools should be organized and how children should be taught. Schools alone cannot address all of a child's developmental needs: the meaningful involvement of parents as facilitators of learning and support from the community are essential. Parents have always played a crucial role in their children's emotional and intellectual development. They serve as their children's first teachers, and give them the stepping stones they need to adapt to life in school.

As the corona virus pandemic puts face-to-face learning to a halt, parents find themselves at the frontlines of education once more.

Parents now have the important task of ensuring that their children receive quality education without compromising their safety. Although education takes a major hit as classrooms are forced to close their doors to eager students, countless parents are stepping up to support their children who are adjusting to the new set-up for the incoming school year (The Manila Times, 2020).

Parental involvement usually refers to the practices of parents, caregivers and guardians when they support their school-aged children. Familial involvement is another term used to identify parents, caregivers and guardians who support children enrolled in some form of virtual schooling (Black, 2009). Learning coaches is a term some education management organizations (EMOs) use to refer to parents, caregivers, and guardians who are the primary supporters of children enrolled in cyber and online charter schooling.

Far less research has addressed to elementary school students' parents with regard to their support and participation in their child's new adaptation of distance learning modality, specifically in science subject, thus it is the intent of the researcher to study.

Methodology

Research Design

The approach of the study is descriptive-quantitative research approach design to describe the status of the specified problems. The researcher aimed at identifying the parents' support and assessing how often they do the specified support on their child's distance learning experience. Parents of the students were personally identified and approached by the researcher to gather the necessary data. The researcher explained to them the objectives and purpose of the study. Then, the researcher provided the instrument which is a researcher-modified survey questionnaire in instrument.

Respondents

Total enumeration sampling technique was used in the study since according to preliminary survey, there are 100 pupils with the same corresponding parents listed. So, this study utilized 100 Grade 5 pupils. The reason why Grade 5 was chosen among grade levels in an elementary context is that, as initially identified or pre-surveyed, the group revealed a unique case of academic performance in Science subject – a number of them got undesirable, desirable, and average performance. This makes them worth the study.

Data Analysis

The data that gathered will be the basis for any academic intervention programs from the school. Also, it will also be a basis for other researchers from different elementary schools to conduct in order to raise awareness on possible support from the parents to escalate their child's academic performance. To the administrators, this will be their guide to craft extension program addressing how to support child's academic performance thru home-based learning.

On the other hand, data was statistically computed with the following statistical tools:

For problems 1, 2, and 3, mean and frequency count test were used.

For problem 4, chi-square test was utilized.

Ethical Considerations

To address ethical issues, the following were the ethical measures done:

The researcher did secure, assent and consent forms from the respondents: parents of the pupils,

The researcher also personally asked the parents of each pupil permission for the utilization of their child's academic performance,

The researcher did personally explain to the respondents involved in the study the objective, purpose, process, and outcome of the study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcome of the quantitative analysis of the research questions answers. The results are presented based on the research problems posed.

Problem 1. What are the parents’ supports to their Grade 5 pupils?

The result of the study reveals that among the identified parents’ supports as to monitoring, volunteering, involvement, progress, and extra help, the last one which is the extra help (look for the materials needed for the completion of the child’s activities and modules: WIFI, and others) gained a frequency count of 91 which ranks as first. Meanwhile, monitoring type of parents’ support by supervising and assessing the records of the child receives a frequency count of 88 which ranks as 2nd. Progress type of parents’ supports (solicit opinions of the teacher in-charge on the development of the child) has a frequency count of 86 which ranks as 3rd and the Volunteering type of parents’ support (get the module from the school to house) ranks as 4th with a frequency count of 85. Lastly, Involvement type of parents’ support receives a frequency count of 82 which ranks as 5th.

The result implies that, all of these identified parents’ support were being rendered by the parents to their children. It can also be noted that the frequency counts of these types of parents’ supports are not far from each other, meaning these are really being exercised by the parents.

Table 1. *Level of the Parents’ Supports*

<i>Parents’ Supports</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Monitoring (Supervising and assessing the records of the child)	88	2nd
Volunteering (Get the module from the school to house)	85	4th
Involvement (Stand at the child’s side and guide him during answering the module)	82	5th
Progress (Solicit opinions of the teacher in-charge on the development of the child)	86	3rd
Extra Help (Look for the materials needed for the completion of the child’s activities and modules: WIFI, and others)	91	1st

Problem 2. How often do their parents participate in supporting their child in their modular distance learning modality?

The result of the study reveals that among all the identified types of parents’ supports as to Monitoring, Volunteering, Involvement, Progress, and Extra Help, only Progress type of parents’ support is interpreted as sometimes being done by the parents to their child with a mean of 3.12; while the rest of the types of parents’ supports are often done by the parents (monitoring – 4.02; Volunteering – 4.16; Involvement – 4.01; and Extra Help – 4.03).

This implies that progress type of parents’ support were at least 4 to 6 times being done by the parents of the child in today’s new learning modality which is modular. On the other hand, Monitoring, Volunteering, Involvement, and Extra Help, were done by the parents at least 7 to 9 times. This further implies that the support system or the concrete support given by the parents of these Grade 5 pupils in Science subject were really observable and it is a good sign that the parents are participative.

Table 2. *Level of occurrences of Parents’ Supports*

<i>Types of Parents’ Supports</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Monitoring	4.02	Often
Volunteering	4.16	Often
Involvement	4.01	Often
Progress	3.12	Sometimes
Extra Help	4.03	Often
Overall	3.87	Often

Scale: 1.00–1.80 (Never) | 1.81–2.60 (Rarely) | 2.61–3.40 (Sometimes) | 3.41–4.20 (Often) | 4.21–5.00 (Always)

Problem 3. What is the level of the academic performance of Grade 5 pupils in Science Subject?

The result of the study reveals that the level of the academic performance of Grade 5 pupils in Science subject got the average of 4.19 which means a very satisfactory grade. This means that most of the students are having high grades since the population receives a very satisfactory grades in Science subject.

Table 3. *Level of academic performance of Grade 5 students in Science subject*

<i>Population (N)</i>	<i>Academic Performance Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Grade 5 Science Subject	4.19	Very Satisfactory

Scale: 1.00–1.80 (Did not meet expectations) | 1.81–2.60 (Fairly Satisfactory) | 2.61–3.40 (Satisfactory) | 3.41–4.20 (Very Satisfactory) | 4.21–5.00 (Outstanding)

Problem 4. Is there a significant influence on the level of occurrence of the parents’ support and their Grade 5 pupils’ academic performance?

On the test of significant influence on the level of occurrence of the parents’ support and the academic performance of the Grade 5 pupils in Science subject, the result reveals that all types of parents’ support only monitoring and extra help types contribute significant

relationship on the level of occurrence of the parents' support and the students' academic performance in their science subject with a p-value lesser than 0.005 level of significance of 0.001 and 0.003; while volunteering, progress, and involvement do not contribute any significant findings since the p-value are greater than 0.005 level of significance, that are 0.171, 0.740, and 0.680 respectively.

This implies that when a parent often supports their child as to supervising and assessing the records of the child (Monitoring) and looking for the materials needed for the completion of the child's activities and modules: WIFI, and others (Extra Help) presents a correlation with the academic performance on science subject. Meaning, the child will get a very satisfactory grade when monitoring and extra help will be given by the parents.

Table 4. *Test of significant influence on the level of occurrence of the parents' support and their Grade 5 pupils' level of academic performance*

	<i>N</i>	<i>rs</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation @ 0.05 level of Significance</i>
Monitoring Students' Performance	100	-.019	.001	Significant
Volunteering Students' Performance	100	-.139	.171	Insignificant
Involvement Students' Performance	100	.034	.740	Insignificant
Progress Students' Performance	100	-.042	.680	Insignificant
ExtraHelp Students' Performance	100	-.036	.003	Significant

Conclusions

This study revealed that the types of parents' supports of the Grade 5 pupils are monitoring (supervising and assessing the records of the child), volunteering (getting the module from the school to house), involvement (standing at the child's side and guide him during answering the module), progress (soliciting opinions of the teacher in-charge on the development of the child), and extra help (looking for the materials needed for the completion of the child's activities and modules: WIFI, and others), and these types were often observed or exercised. On the other hand, the level of academic performance of the Grade 5 pupils in Science subject is very satisfactory. This study also found out that there are significant influences of the monitoring and extra help types of parents' supports to the academic performance of the Grade 5 pupils implying that when these types of supports are continuously be given by the parents, the academic performance of the pupils will also be improved.

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